

PREPARATION OF ANODIC OXIDE FILM ON Ti-6Al-4V VIA ANODIZATION IN MONOCALCIUMPHOSPHATE MONOHYDRATE (MCPM) ELECTROLYTE

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1 Introduction

Ti-6Al-4V alloy has been widely used as dental implant materials due to its good mechanical properties, high corrosion resistance and excellent biocompatibility [1]. However, because Ti-6Al-4V has no ability to bond to living bone directly, the coating methods using bioactive materials have been applied for improving its tissue compatibility. Cell and tissue responses are affected by the chemical properties of the implants surfaces and the surface topography of the implants, therefore, the surface is much more important in biocompatibility of titanium implant than the bulk titanium itself [2-4].

Anodization is one of an important surface modification technique which is a superior and cheap method in terms of its capacity to form rough and porous oxide surfaces that could bond to human bone directly, and also form thick and uniform coatings at ambient temperatures. Moreover, this technique used for preparing anodic oxide film will rapidly promote the surface roughness and not cost-consuming. The study of anodizing at low current density found that there were mix oxides film of Ti deposited on Ti-6Al-4V [1-5].

Anodic oxide films on Ti substrate formed by electrochemical methods have been studied for many years in order to improve the biocompatibility of dental implant. Because the anodic oxide film can increase surface roughness, decrease the contact angle and fulfill the strong adhesion of the film coating on Ti-6Al-4V. The surface roughness and wettability of implant may influence the contact between Ti-6Al-4V alloy and living tissues which is so called osseointegration optimized by treating surface [6-8]. The study of the influence of the surface roughness to protein absorption has been founded that Ti alloy which had better surface

roughness would absorb higher amount of fibronectin than the Ti alloy which had smooth surface. Moreover, the surface roughness also enhance the hydrophilicity.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the preparation of anodic oxide film on Ti-6Al-4V via anodization in Monocalciumphosphate monohydrate (MCPM) electrolyte at different low current densities (0.25, 0.5, 1, 1.5 and 2 mA/cm²). The effects of anodization at low current density which has not been paid much attention by any researchers will be reported in this paper. Moreover, the surface roughness, the hydrophilicity and the surface topography of anodic oxide film on Ti-6Al-4V prepared in MCPM electrolyte were also investigated.

2 Experimental procedure

The working electrode used in the present study was made of Ti-6Al-4V sheets with 1×8×20 mm³ and they were mechanically polished with emery papers (grade 1200) and No. 170 diamond plate, washed with distilled water in ultrasonic bath for 15 minutes and dried at a room temperature. Before anodizing, the working electrode was etched in 1M HF for 1 minute and washed with distilled water, then finally dipped in a three-electrode cell. A small piece of platinum (1.0 cm²) was used as a counter electrode (CE) and Ag/AgCl was used as a reference electrode (RE). The anodization process was operated using Galvanostat-Potentiostat connected to a computer and operated by GPEs program (PGstat30, Metrohm Siam Ltd.). The electrolyte was solution of monocalcium phosphate monohydrate [(MCPM, Ca(H₂PO₄)₂•H₂O), Fluka, 85% purity] in different

concentrations (from 0.5 to 5 Molar and saturated solution) and different pH as shown in Table 1. After that the saturated solution was kept overnight before filtering to separate the precipitate, then the MCPM solution was obtained. The solution temperature is 26°C at room temperature.

Table 1. The pH of MCPM electrolyte at different concentration.

MCPM (Molar)	pH
0.5	2.20
1	2.07
3	1.80
5	1.10
Saturated	1.01

Anodization was carried out at low different current densities of 0.25, 0.5, 1, 1.5 and 2 mA/cm² for duration of 30 minutes at room temperature. After coating, Ti-6Al-4V substrates were rinsed in distilled water for several times to remove residual electrolyte and dried at room temperature.

The hydrophilicity of the film surface was determined by the contact angle of distilled water droplet, measured by a contact angle meters (Ramehart). The surface of the anodic oxide film was measured by scanning electron microscope (SEM: JSM-6480LV, JEOL, Japan). Finally, the surface topography and roughness were examined by atomic force microscopy (AFM: Nanoscope 4).

3 Results

Anodization is the technique used to improve the surface property of titanium alloy, moreover, various oxide layer is also formed on the surface. In case of dental implants study, the osseointegration was influenced by the roughness and hydrophilicity of the surface. Ti metal which is the main component in Ti-6Al-4V alloy will always react with H₂O or air and become covered with a protective oxide layer. The native oxide film was formed on titanium when exposed to the atmosphere such as polishing or etching. During anodizing, the native oxide film was dissolved and then the self-passivated film was formed [9]. This study found that after anodizing,

the colour of anodized film revealed gold colour when applied current density at 0.25 to 1.5 mA/cm² and revealed blue colour at 2 mA/cm². The colour of these films varied with the voltage operation, it was found that during anodizing if the voltage overload reached up more than 10V, the colour of the film would be cyan blue which was obtain in case of applying current density at 2 mA/cm² [10-11].

Fig.1. The open circuit potentials showed anodization of Ti-6Al-4V in selected condition of saturated MCPM electrolyte at 1mA/cm².

Formation of anodic oxide film on Ti-6Al-4V included two processes of corrosion on the open-circuit potential versus time curves, as shown in Figure 1. The voltage-time responded for anodic oxide film in saturated MCPM solution to various voltages. Firstly, the circuit potential was rapidly increased in range of 0 to 250 seconds which meant the corrosion on surface was quickly happened and the formation of anodized film was formed when the reaction time went by. Secondly, the circuit potential became constant as the corrosion decreased due to the passive oxide formed on the surface.

Fig.2. Scrape adhesion test of oxide film prepared MCPM electrolyte at different current density.

Figure 2 showed the relationship between the current density and the applied load of anodic oxide film prepared in saturated and 1 Molar of MCPM electrolyte at different current density. Applying the current density made the applied load of the anodic oxide film increased in both of two concentrations. It was observed that higher current density provided the better adhesion of anodic oxide film on substrate.

The hydrophilicity of the implant will affect cell and tissue around the implant which living with the human body fluid. Table 2 showed the water contact angle of the anodic oxide film which was operated at different current density in different concentration of MCPM electrolyte. Figure 3 showed the contact angle tendency of the anodic oxide film formed in 0.5M, 1M and saturated MCPM electrolyte at low current density. The anodic oxide film formed at current density of 0.25, 0.5, 1, 1.5 and 2 mA/cm²

presented that the contact angle decreased while increased the current density. It was indicated that increasing of the current density could enhance the hydrophilicity of Ti-6Al-4V. Because the tendency of the contact angle operated in saturated MCPM electrolyte was similar to both operated in 0.5M and 1M of MCPM electrolyte, so this work selected this three conditions to investigate the surface topography and the surface roughness continually.

Figure 4-6 showed SEM micrographs of anodic oxide film on Ti-6Al-4V surface showed that surface roughness increased after anodizing in all samples. Anodic oxide film formed in case of 2 mA/cm² (Figure 4d, 5d, 6d) showed better surface roughness than the other formed which is according to the nature of Ti metal, a main component in Ti-6Al-4V alloy that will be rapidly dissolved by strong and even weak acids. It was indicated that

Table 2. The water contact angle of anodic oxide film at different current density

<i>Angle (°)</i>		<i>Angle (°)</i>		<i>Angle (°)</i>	
<i>(a) 0.5M MCPM</i>		<i>(c) 3M MCPM</i>		<i>(e) Saturated MCPM</i>	
Control	75.8	Control	75.8	Control	75.8
0.25mA/cm ²	64.6	0.25mA/cm ²	59.2	0.25mA/cm ²	61.1
0.5 mA/cm ²	65.7	0.5 mA/cm ²	58.0	0.5 mA/cm ²	59.2
1 mA/cm ²	57.4	1 mA/cm ²	54.8	1 mA/cm ²	55.2
1.5 mA/cm ²	53.0	1.5 mA/cm ²	54.2	1.5 mA/cm ²	54.9
2 mA/cm ²	54.5	2 mA/cm ²	52.4	2 mA/cm ²	52.3
<i>(b) 1M MCPM</i>		<i>(d) 5M MCPM</i>			
Control	75.8	Control	75.8		
0.25mA/cm ²	57.9	0.25mA/cm ²	57.7		
0.5 mA/cm ²	58.4	0.5 mA/cm ²	62.4		
1 mA/cm ²	58.3	1 mA/cm ²	58.6		
1.5 mA/cm ²	53.2	1.5 mA/cm ²	54.9		
2 mA/cm ²	52.4	2 mA/cm ²	52.7		

anodization could enhance the surface roughness on the Ti-6Al-4V surface and high current density was also beneficial for the surface roughness of the film.

Fig.3. The contact angle of anodic oxide film in MCPM solution at different current

Fig.4. SEM micrographs of anodic oxide film on Ti-6Al-4V surface in saturated MCPM electrolyte : (a) before anodization (b) 0.25 mA/cm² (c) 1 mA/cm² (d) 2 mA/cm²

Fig.5. SEM micrographs of anodic oxide film on Ti-6Al-4V surface in 0.5M MCPM electrolyte : (a) before anodization (b) 0.25 mA/cm² (c) 1 mA/cm² (d) 2 mA/cm²

Fig.6. SEM micrographs of anodic oxide film on Ti-6Al-4V surface in 1M MCPM electrolyte : (a) before anodization (b) 0.25 mA/cm² (c) 1 mA/cm² (d) 2 mA/cm²

Figure 7 showed AFM micrographs of anodic oxide film on Ti-6Al-4V surface in three condition : saturated, 0.5M and 1M MCPM. These data revealed that high current density was beneficial for the surface roughness of the film. Anodic oxide film formed at 2 mA/cm² (Figure d) showed better surface roughness than the other formed. It was observed that anodization could enhance the surface roughness on the Ti-6Al-4V surface and high current density was also beneficial for the surface roughness of the film.

Fig.7. AFM micrographs of anodic oxide film on Ti-6Al-4V surface at various conditions: (a) before anodization (b) saturated MCPM, 0.25 mA/cm² (c) saturated MCPM, 1 mA/cm² (d) saturated MCPM, 2 mA/cm² (e) 0.5M MCPM, 0.25 mA/cm² (f) 0.5M MCPM, 1 mA/cm² (g) 0.5M MCPM, 2 mA/cm² (h) 1M MCPM, 0.25 mA/cm² (i) 1M MCPM, 1 mA/cm² (j) 1M MCPM, 2 mA/cm²

This work found that the small amount of MCPM reagent, which was added in electrolyte, also can produce the anodic oxide film. The surface roughness and the hydrophilicity of the film was approximately with the film formed in saturated MCPM electrolyte. It was indicated that less MCPM reagent can also promote the properties of the anodic oxide film. From these data, it helps to save the amount of the MCPM reagent when anodization at low current density.

In dental implant, the influence of the surface roughness to protein absorption has been studied and founded that Ti alloy which had better surface roughness would absorb higher amount of fibronectin than the Ti alloy which had smooth surface. Moreover, the surface roughness also enhance the hydrophilicity [12]. From these data, it was conformed to this study and concluded that high current density was also beneficial for the surface roughness and the hydrophilicity of the oxide film.

4 Conclusions

Anodic oxide film was obtained on Ti-6Al-4V by anodization from MCPM electrolyte at different

low current densities and different electrolyte concentration. The result founded that, operating at 2 mA/cm² of MCPM electrolyte could promote the better surface roughness and hydrophilicity of anodic oxide film. It was revealed from the analysis of AFM that high current density was also beneficial for the surface roughness of the anodic oxide film. Moreover, the surface roughness also enhance the hydrophilicity of the anodic oxide film which might provide the osseointegration to the implant.

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